

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this certificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

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NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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